

SHUKUR KHOLMIRZAYEV'S LIFE AND WORK

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ABSTRACT: *Shukur Kholmirzayev is a well-known writer who made a great contribution to the development of Uzbek literature of the 20th century. He has a special place in the spiritual development of the Uzbek people with his unique prose created with high artistic skill. Sh.Kholmirzayev, J.London, E.Hemingway, S.Thompson among the famous writers of the world created unique works on the theme of nature, which is a particularly noticeable edge of the writer's creativity. researched through the stories of their relationships.*

Key words: *Shukur Kholmirzayev, Boysun, Surkhan Eli, Uzbek, nature and man, story, cruelty, creative principle.*

Shukur Kholmirzaev was born on March 24, 1940 in Boysun district of Surkhandarya region. People's writer of Uzbekistan (1991). Graduated from Tashkent University Faculty of Journalism (1963). The first stories and essays were published in 1958. "White Horse" (1962), "Waves" (1963), "Who is not eighteen?" (1965) short stories, as well as the stories written by the writer during this period "Under the Distant Stars" (1971), "Life Forever" (1974), "If a Heavy Stone Moves..." (1980), "Roads, satellites" (1984), "Almond blossomed in winter" (1986), "It snowed in the mountains" (1987). Novels such as "Last Stop" (1976), "Kil Priprik" (1984), "Passenger" (1987), "Olaboji" (1992), "Dinosaur" (Book 1, 1996) the author. There are also the dramas "Black Belt" (1987), "Party" (staged in 1990). Kholmirzayev's first stories and essays were published in 1958. In the early period of his work, Kholmirzayev used his pen in the short story genre as well as the story, and wrote the short stories "Aq otli" (1962),

"Tolqinlar" (1963), "Who is not included in ten eight?" (1965). These works are among the best examples of Uzbek short stories of the 60s. The stories written by the writer during this period were later "Under the Distant Stars" (1971), "Life is Eternal" (1974), "If a Heavy Stone Moves..." (1980), "Roads, Companions" (1984), "Almond Blooms in Winter" (1986)., "It Snowed in the Mountains" (1987) took place in his collections. Kholmirezayev's stories and stories, on the one hand, express the unique romance of his youth and student years, and on the other hand, the life, struggles and changes in society and the spiritual world of the people of different nature living in Boysun district, where the writer was born and raised, found his artistic interpretation. Later, the life of Boysun and the people of Boysun became the main theme of Kholmirezayev's work, and became an important factor in the fact that the realistic image became the priority in the writer's work. As Kholmirezayev discovered the complex life processes in reality and the spiritual world of people with conflicts, the romantic pathos in his early stories gave way to realism and created an opportunity for the writer to bring elements of "brutal realism" into Uzbek literature. In his works created in the 80s and 90s, he gave a deep artistic analysis of the society and people's life of that period.

Kholmirezayev wrote novels such as "Last Stop" (1976), "Kil Bridge" (1984), "Passenger" (1987), "Olaboji" (1992), "Dinosaur" (1 book, 1996). H.'s novels "Last Station", "Yo'lovchi" and "Olaboji" showed the collapse of the Soviet society from the inside by the 70s and 80s through bright artistic images. The social issue raised in these novels found its new artistic interpretation in the writer's novel "Dinosaur". The story of the struggle of conflicts in the life and spiritual world of a person who sincerely believed that the Shora state was a people-friendly state, and that the internal and external policies he pursued were policies that served the interests of the people and the country are at the center of this novel. began to study his future. This theme was expressed in the writer's novel "Kil Kuprik" and the play "Black Belt" (1987). The tragedy of lost people is vividly embodied in their images. The play "Black belt" staged at the Abror Hidoyatov Youth Theater based on H.'s play played an important role in the emergence of a new approach to the historical past in the young generation.

Kholmirezayev's play "Banquet" dedicated to the tragic fate of Uzbek women during the Soviet era was also staged at the Youth Theater (1990).

Kholmirezayev in recent years Sh. Burkhanov, B. Zakirov, R. Choriyev, Shuhrat, O. Yakubov, O'. He wrote essays and literary criticism articles about such well-known figures of literature and art as Umarbekov, A. Oripov, M. Koshjanov. Although Kholmirezayev wrote a number of works in the novel genre and these works have a special place in the history of Uzbek novelists of this period, he is primarily a story writer. In his stories, he continued the best traditions of Uzbek writers such as A. Qadiri, A. Qahhor, and enriched Uzbek storytelling with the artistic experiences of Russian and European writers. The best stories of H. are distinguished by the new and bright image of the hero, the originality of the composition, the colorful language of the characters. The first short story "White Horse" was published in 1962. His second work - "Waves" (1963) was praised by Abdulla Qahhor. 1976), "The Lame Crane" (1978), "Dirt Streets" (1978), "The Language of the Bird" (1982), "The Last Days of the Hero" (1984), "The Mountains Snowed" (1986), "The Last Son of Abdullah Nabi" "Days" (1983), "Esiz, Eshniyoz!" (1988), "Cloud-blocked Moon" (1997), "Last Station" (1976), "Kil Kuprik" (1984), "Olaboji" (1991), " Novels such as "Dinosaur" (1996), the drama "Black Belt" (1989), "Wild Flower", "Spring Has Passed", "Bitiktosh", "Freedom", "Uzbeks", "Life is Forever", "If a Heavy Stone Moves" , dozens of stories such as "Teacher", "Blue Sea", "Smile", "The Dew Fallen Bedazor", "Boychechak Opened", "The Owner of the Horse", "Navroz, Navroz" and many other works were published. In his works, the national character of the Uzbeks, the relationship between man and nature are deeply artistically interpreted. In the 60s, when Shukur Kholmirezayev's story-telling was just forming, he chose the subject of nature and man for more of his works. After reading the works of Shukur Kholmirezayev, the person who steps into the oasis of Surkhan, Boysun mountains, endless steppes, where the writer grew up, sees the scenery, colors, hears strange melodies, all of them "kick" in his heart. standing" clearly feels that it is taken from the "warm" bosom of nature.

Shukur Kholmirezayev himself was a person who deeply understood his life and could sense the change in the human spirit. That's why in his works he works on the basis of the laws of nature, he draws conclusions that this naturalness should never be violated, and if it is violated, it can cause great disasters and tragedies.

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